

Original Article

Role of Faculty Diversity in Students Learning at University Level

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Abstract

Faculty diversity enhances students' learning by exposing them to a wide range of perspectives, experiences, and teaching approaches, fostering critical thinking and cultural awareness. This study was conducted to find out the role of faculty diversity in students learning at university level. The objectives of the study were to identify the diversity in faculty; to assess the level of students' learning and to find out the role of faculty diversity in students' learning at university level. This study was descriptive and survey method was used. The population of the study consisted of one hundred seventy-five (175) teachers of University of Kotli AJ&K. the researchers selected one hundred twenty-one (121) teachers as sample by using simple random sampling technique. A questionnaire was used as a research instrument to collect data. After ensuring validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the researchers personally collected the data from all the teachers. The data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researchers used frequency, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data. It was found that faculty diversity enhances student learning experiences at the university level by fostering inclusive perceptions, promoting critical thinking, and preparing students for a globalized world. Teachers disagreed that they regularly update their teaching methods to improve students learning. It is recommended that the diverse faculty members may serve as role models for students from various backgrounds, promoting inclusivity and fostering a sense of belonging. They may vary teaching approaches which may lead to enriched classroom discussions, improved critical thinking skills.

Keywords: Faculty Diversity, Students' Learning, Enhanced Learning Environment

Introduction

The world is like a global village these days. People from different backgrounds and customs can easily meet and connect with one another. Students from all walks of life from all over the world can meet, learn, and share their unique perspectives at universities, which are similar to the same replication. This blending of many cultures and viewpoints contributes to a rich and dynamic learning environment that is sufficient to expand students' worldviews. At the same time that the global village brings people closer together, universities are places where a wide range of perspectives come together to form a community that is much more connected. The world has evolved into a "global village" where people from various cultures, backgrounds, and viewpoints come together. Because universities have evolved into melting pots of various cultures, backgrounds, and viewpoints, this diversity is replicated there (Hurtado, 2001).

Hurtado (2001) states that universities need to encourage an environment that respects academic quality, cultural competence, and social responsibility. In shaping our societies and institutions, diversity is essential. As boundaries are blurred and cultures interact, educational institutions, particularly universities, have become miniatures of this global diversity. This inclusive truth is well shown in student bodies, faculties, and curricula in

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universities around the world, thus generating a rich environment of learning and experience (Gurin, Dey, Hurtado, & Gurin, 2002).

Faculty diversity is a significant component of this effort-to the existence of faculty members with backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives (Milem, 2003). Faculty diversity is important for creating wide-ranging learning environments that support student learning, which is the developments and outcomes of student engagement with the academic content, faculty, and peers (Kuh, 2008).

Research shows that faculty diversity has positive influences on students' outcomes related to learning, on their academic achievement, cognitive development, and social growth (Gurin *et al.*, 2002). The research by Gurin *et al.* (2002) found that the more experiences of the students to faculty from diverse background led to higher levels of the cognitive development and social growth than those evident to the less interaction with peers on the same. Similarly, Hurtado (2012) found that faculty diversity was completely related to student academic success and sense of belonging.

These relationships between diversity have many different facets, and diverse faculties can serve as mentors or role models for young, gifted students from a range of backgrounds and practices (Milem, 2003). According to Hurtado (2012), this can inspire, involve, and give students a sense of belonging. Diversity in the faculty may present an opportunity to persuade students to confront their preconceptions and prejudices by fostering a critical thinking environment that promotes academic progress (Gurin *et al.*, 2002).

Furthermore, pedagogy and curriculum can be impacted by faculty diversity, resulting in more inclusive and culturally sensitive teaching methods. Research suggests that teachers who were sensitive to cultural differences and held their students to high standards had a positive effect on their academic performance (Gay, 2010).

Additionally, faculty diversity affects campus climate by generally promoting a more diverse campus and learning environment for students. Students who perceive their campus as inclusive and welcoming report feeling more a part of the community and performing better academically (Hurtado, 2012). Thus, to put it briefly, diversity is one of the main aspects of university life that enhances students' learning.

Diversity in faculty and student learning is still a complicated, multidimensional topic that requires further study and analysis. Indeed, faculty diversity continues to be a vital source of inspiration for developing inclusive learning environments in universities that inspire students to achieve and feel empowered. Diverse faculty members enhance the academic experience and aid in the development of students' more complete worldviews by bringing their distinct viewpoints, experiences, and cultural understandings to the classroom (Gurin *et al.*, 2002).

Faculty members can be a significant source of motivation for students from marginalized communities, providing them with a feeling of acceptance and approval (Gasman *et al.*, 2015). More significantly, a diverse faculty can eliminate implicit biases and stereotypes, improve the learning environment and foster social cohesion (Smith, 2018). In today's globalization model, students who have been exposed to different perspectives from their teachers develop critical thinking, teamwork, and cultural competency skills (Antonio *et al.*, 2004).

Faculty diversity is one such important issue that is not only one of impartiality but also has a significant impact on academic success and excellence. Numerous scholars have conducted thorough investigations into various aspects of faculty diversity. Because there still appears to be a remarkable gap in understanding the precise impact of faculty diversity on higher-level student learning. In order to close this gap, this study aims to understand how a diverse faculty affects students' academic performance, engagement, and overall educational experiences at the University of Kotli Azad in Jammu and Kashmir.

Statement of the Problem

Even though the value of diverse faculty in higher education is becoming more widely recognized, little is known about the precise impact that diverse faculty have on university students' learning outcomes. The recent studies show that diversity helps students become more creative, critical thinkers, and culturally capable, more empirical research is required to fully comprehend the ways in which faculty diversity affects many aspects of student learning, such as engagement, retention, and academic success. This study looked at how elements like faculty demographics, teaching philosophies, and viewpoints help to create a comprehensive and motivating learning environment. Therefore, this study was conducted to explore the role of faculty diversity in student learning at University of Kotli.

Objectives of the Study

Following were the objectives of the study:

1. To identify the diversity in faculty at university level.
2. To assess the level of students' learning at university level.
3. To find out the role of faculty diversity in students' learning at university level.

Research Questions

1. To what extent there is a diversity in the faculty at university level?
2. What is the level of students learning at university level?
3. What is the role of faculty diversity at university level?

Review of the Related Literature

Diversity

Differences in race, ethnicity, gender, age, socioeconomic status, physical capabilities, sexual orientation, education, and religion are all examples of diversity. To be inclusive, it involves acknowledging, valuing, and respecting these distinctions. Diversity is defined as "the variety of personal experiences, values, and worldviews that arise from differences of culture and circumstance" by the American Psychological Association (American Psychological Association, 2020).

Diversity includes the variety of human differences and how these differences intersect. According to Milem, Chang, and Antonio (2005), classroom diversity (incorporating different viewpoints into curricula), interactional diversity (interpersonal interactions among diverse groups), and structural diversity (numerical representation of diverse groups) are all examples of diversity in higher education.

Faculty Diversity

In academic institutions, faculty diversity is the presence of people from different backgrounds, such as socioeconomic status, gender, sexual orientation, race, and ethnicity. Research has demonstrated that encouraging faculty diversity improves educational outcomes, creates inclusive learning environments, and expands the range of viewpoints in teaching and research (Smith, 2018). It is employed to characterize the diverse backgrounds, identities, and experiences of the teaching staff. This diversity encompasses socioeconomic status, gender, sexual orientation, race, ethnicity, and disability status (Gurin *et al.*, 2002).

The term "teacher diversity" describes how various demographic groups, such as race, ethnicity, gender, and socioeconomic status, are represented among educators. Diversity is important because it benefits students from different backgrounds by bringing different viewpoints, role models, and cultural competence into the classroom (Kraft & Rogers, 2015). Diverse teachers may improve minority students' academic performance, graduation rates, and discipline disparities, according to research (Dee, 2004; Gershenson, Hart, Lindsay, & Papageorge, 2017).

For students from comparable backgrounds, diverse educators can act as mentors and role models, offering support and motivation (Dee, 2004). In conclusion, diverse teachers are crucial to creating inclusive learning environments and enhancing outcomes for all students, especially those from underrepresented groups.

Faculty Diversity at University Level

Diversity among university teachers is an important component of higher education that affects both institutional efficacy and student success. A diverse faculty complements the learning environment, fosters cultural competency, and supports each student's academic and social growth by contributing a range of perspectives and experiences (Antonio, 2002). It has been demonstrated that having faculty members with similar backgrounds helps students from underrepresented groups feel more included and confident in their academic abilities (Umbach, 2006).

Because of the possible effects it may have on students' learning outcomes, faculty diversity at universities has gained significant attention. According to research, a diverse faculty can improve student learning by offering a range of viewpoints, mentorship opportunities, and role models (Smith, 2018). According to studies, students from underrepresented backgrounds frequently gain social and academic advantages when they interact with instructors who have comparable experiences or backgrounds. Increased engagement, retention rates, and general academic success among the diverse student populations can result from this beneficial influence. Diversity among university

faculty is known to have a significant impact on students' learning outcomes, academic performance, and general understandings of education. According to studies like Smith (2018), a diverse faculty offers a range of viewpoints, role models, and mentorship opportunities.

Diverse faculty members also contribute to more inclusive teaching methods and a more comprehensive curriculum. They are more likely to challenge stereotypes, support students from a variety of backgrounds, and integrate diverse viewpoints into their classes (Gurin *et al.*, 2002). In addition to helping minority students, diversity exposes all students to a range of perspectives and approaches to problem-solving, preparing them for success in a globalized workforce (Milem, Chang, & Antonio, 2005).

Even with the acknowledged advantages, increasing faculty diversity is still difficult. The hiring process's structural injustices, the lack of assistance for minority faculty, and the larger social problems of gender and ethnic discrimination are some of the obstacles. Through policies and practices that promote equity and inclusion, universities must make deliberate and ongoing efforts to recruit, retain, and support diverse faculty members in order to address these issues (Smith, 2018).

Significance of Students Learning at University Level

For students, university education is extremely important because it gives them the information, abilities, and critical thinking skills necessary for both professional and personal success. Universities provide a controlled setting where students can study their chosen subjects in great detail, leading to a deeper comprehension and level of expertise that is generally unachievable in earlier educational stages. This advanced education fosters a lifelong love of learning in addition to preparing students for the particular careers, which is essential in a labor market that is constantly changing (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005).

Universities are essential for social and personal growth in addition to academic knowledge. They offer a unique setting where students can engage with classmates from various backgrounds, promoting interpersonal skills and cultural awareness. In order to prepare students for the globalized workforce, where cooperation and communication with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds are critical, these interactions are crucial. Thus, attending college helps people become well-rounded individuals who can make valuable contributions to society (Kuh, 2001).

Finally, there are many long-term advantages to a university education, such as improved career prospects and increased earning potential. Research has repeatedly demonstrated that people who have a university degree typically make more money overall than people who don't. Additionally, university graduates tend to have higher employment rates and more opportunities for career advancement when they graduate. These financial advantages highlight the importance of funding higher education for both individuals and society at large (Oreopoulos & Petronijevic, 2013).

Teacher Diversity and Student Learning at University Level

The learning outcomes and experiences of university students can be greatly impacted by the diversity of teachers. In addition to creating inclusive curricula and improving learning environments, a diverse faculty can contribute a range of viewpoints that enhance scholarly discourse. Students may learn more effectively if teachers are more diverse. According to Gurin, Dey, Hurtado, and Gurin (2002), a diverse teaching staff can contribute to a more comprehensive learning environment that encourages critical thinking and expands students' perspectives.

A diverse faculty can boost students from underrepresented groups' sense of belonging and academic motivation by serving as role models. This portrayal can lessen feelings of alienation and exclusion. Students who are exposed to a diverse teaching staff may become more culturally competent. This ability equips students to work well in a variety of settings and is essential in today's globalized society (Hurtado, 2012).

Because diverse faculty members offer a wider range of role models and perspectives, they can aid in challenging and reducing ethnic and cultural stereotypes. The campus environment may become more welcoming as a result (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005). According to research, when a diverse faculty teaches a class, students are more involved and actively participate. According to Umbach (2006), this involvement is associated with improved academic achievement and increased satisfaction with their educational involvement. Students can develop their critical thinking abilities by being exposed to a variety of perspectives and problem-solving

techniques from a diverse teaching staff. According to Antonio *et al.* (2004), intellectual growth and problem-solving skills benefit from this diversity of viewpoints.

Relationship between Faculty Diversity and Student Learning at University Level

Numerous studies have been conducted on the connection between student learning and faculty diversity. Students from similar backgrounds can look up to faculty members from different backgrounds, which can inspire motivation and a sense of community. At the collegiate level, the importance of teacher diversity in influencing student learning outcomes is becoming more widely acknowledged. University faculty diversity includes a range of characteristics, such as gender, race, ethnicity, and cultural background, all of which enhance the educational process (Smith, 2018). The ability to provide students from different backgrounds with diverse role models is one of the main advantages of teacher diversity, as it increases students' motivation and sense of fit. Students who are exposed to a diverse faculty are better prepared for a globalized world by developing critical thinking skills and a wider perspective, according to research.

Apart from improving learning outcomes, diversity among teachers is essential for dispelling prejudices and stereotypes in the classroom. Preconceived ideas are challenged and a more inclusive academic culture is fostered when students interact with faculty members from a variety of backgrounds who are accomplished in their fields. Furthermore, a more inclusive curriculum that takes into account a variety of viewpoints and experiences is developed with the help of diverse faculty. In addition to enhancing academic content, this inclusive approach equips students to succeed in diverse post-graduation workplaces (Smith, 2018).

Research has indicated that student academic achievement and faculty diversity are positively correlated (Smith *et al.*, 1997). The distinct viewpoints that diverse faculty members bring to the classroom can improve discussions and instructional strategies. Students' cultural competency is improved by exposure to a diverse faculty, preparing them for a globalized workforce (Banks, 2015). This exposure cultivates consideration and respect for diverse perspectives and life experiences. Through the presentation of varied perspectives and the questioning of students' presumptions, diverse faculty promote critical thinking (Hurtado, 2001).

Methods and Procedures of the Study

This study was descriptive by nature and cross-sectional survey method was used to collect the data. The population of the study was consisted of 175 teachers of University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The researchers used simple random sampling technique for the selection of the sample and selected a total of 121 teachers as a sample of the study. A questionnaire was consisted of 30 statements. The reliability of the instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha statistical technique and the value was 0.83. After determining the questionnaire validity and reliability the researchers personally visited all the department and collect the data from students. The researcher analyzed data through Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 by using mean score, frequency and percentage for the analysis of data.

Results

Following are the results obtained from data keeping in view the objectives and research questions of the study.

Table 1
Diversity in Faculty

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean	SD
1	The faculty at my university represents a wide range of cultural background	121	4.60	.652
2	The faculty at my university represents diverse ethnic background	121	4.49	.579
3	Faculty diversity contributes towards a rich innovative environment at my university	121	4.50	.593
4	The faculty consists of individuals with diverse educational qualifications	121	4.37	.579
5	There is a good representation of faculty from different age groups at the university	121	4.40	.571
6	The university has policies that promote diversity in faculty hiring	121	4.31	.719

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean	SD
7	Faculty from different socioeconomic backgrounds are valued at my institution	121	2.29	1.143
8	The university's faculty includes members with diverse teaching styles	121	4.40	.652
9	There is a variety of professional experiences among the faculty members	121	4.15	.654
10	The university provides equal opportunities for faculty regardless of their background	121	3.80	.862

The results of Table 1 indicated that the teachers agreed with most of the statements as the mean values of nine out of ten statements were greater than 3.5, which ultimately specified that the teachers were having diversity among them. However, they disagreed with a statement, “Faculty from different socioeconomic backgrounds are valued at my institution” with the mean value of less than 2.5.

Table 2

Students' Learning

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean	SD
1	There are opportunities of diverse students' learning	121	4.67	.538
2	Students are exposed to a broader range of ideas	121	4.37	.565
3	Students understand different cultural perspectives in my university	121	4.35	.558
4	There is a culture of open-mindedness among students	121	4.23	.692
5	Students are able to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios	121	2.01	.944
6	Faculty frequently assess students' understanding through quizzes and tests	121	4.61	.637
7	Faculty members regularly update their teaching methods to improve student learning	121	2.16	.940
8	The university provides opportunities for students to learn beyond the classroom	121	4.25	.710
9	The faculty encourages students to pursue innovative learning approaches	121	4.16	.695
10	Students are comfortable asking questions in class	121	4.39	.830

The results of Table 2 indicated that the teachers agreed with most of the statements as the mean values of eight out of ten statements were greater than 3.5, which ultimately specified that the students were learning in the university. However, they disagreed with the statements, “Students are able to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios” and “Faculty members regularly update their teaching methods to improve student learning” with the mean values of less than 2.5.

Table 3

Role of Faculty Diversity in Students' Learning

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean	SD
1	Diverse faculty perspectives enhance the learning experience of students	121	4.65	.528
2	Faculty diversity contributes to more inclusive classroom discussions	121	4.39	.583
3	Faculty diversity helps students develop a global perspective	121	4.28	.609
4	Faculty diversity positively influences students' critical thinking skills	121	4.42	.559
5	Students feel more comfortable discussing sensitive topics with diverse faculty members	121	4.31	.633
6	Faculty diversity improves students' problem-solving skills	121	4.45	.618

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean	SD
7	Students are more motivated when taught by faculty from diverse backgrounds	121	4.40	.664
8	Diverse faculty members serve as role models for students	121	2.15	.972
9	Students benefit from being taught by diverse faculty members.	121	4.03	.682
10	Students feel academically challenged by diverse faculty teaching methods	121	2.01	.953

The results of Table 3 indicated that the teachers agreed with most of the statements as the mean values of eight out ten statements were greater than 3.5, which ultimately specified that there was a role of teachers’ diversity in students’ learning. However, they disagreed with the statements, “Diverse faculty members serve as role models for students” and “Students feel academically challenged by diverse faculty teaching methods” with the mean values of less than 2.5.

Conclusions

Following conclusions are drawn on the basis of results.

1. It is concluded that there is a high level of agreement among teachers regarding the representation of cultural diversity within the faculty at the university. A significant majority of teachers believe that the faculty comprises individuals from a wide range of cultural backgrounds, reflecting a commitment to fostering an inclusive environment. Faculty members are also perceived to have diverse ethnic backgrounds, further enhancing the inclusive nature of the university. The broad agreement among teachers suggests that the institution has taken effective steps toward promoting diversity, which is critical for creating a dynamic learning environment. This diversity is likely to contribute positively to the overall educational experience.
2. It is concluded that teachers recognize the diversity of educational qualifications and age representations among faculty members. This diversity represents a richness of perspectives and expertise available to students. Strong support for these statements suggests that teachers recognize the value of a diverse faculty in fostering an enriched academic experience. There are significant concerns regarding the valuation of faculty from different socioeconomic backgrounds. Teachers feel that the faculty from different socioeconomic statuses are not valued appropriately. This gap is an area where the university needs to improve to make its environment more inclusive.
3. It is concluded that Faculty diversity was concluded to positively impact the effect on student learning. Teachers said that a faculty is a richer source of teaching and learning that exposes students to a broader idea range, leading to the notion that a diverse faculty enhances the experiences of students, which is also an acknowledgment of the important contribution of faculty diversity in the student's educational development. Mixed opinions surround the role of diverse faculty in acting as role models and mentors to students. Although most teachers concur that diverse faculty are useful additions to the discussion and the learning process, many still feel that teaching students with diverse faculty members does not really have any strong advantages for students. This indicates a chasm the institution should research and expand to be able to bring out maximum fruits of diversity through faculty towards academic success for their students.
4. It is concluded that faculty members believe that the university they fail to continually renew their pedagogies in order to improve students' learning. There is considerable disagreement with this view, but there is consensus among teachers about the university providing students with significant opportunities for learning outside of the classroom. Most teachers feel that students feel free to ask questions in class, indicating a comfortable and supportive learning environment. The mean scores also reflect the same view by highlighting strengths in student engagement and extracurricular learning opportunities.

Recommendations

Following recommendations are made on the basis of conclusion

1. The university administration needs to address for the concerns of non-recognition for faculty from various socioeconomic backgrounds. This can be done by promoting the policies that enhance socioeconomic diversity in hiring faculty, and also, through recognition and valuing faculty from different socioeconomic statuses. In a more holistic approach to the appreciation of faculty, there could be mentoring programs or recognition of faculty with unique views on issues coming from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds.

2. Many instructors report that faculty are not updating the methods of instruction. The university administration needs to invest in professional development activities that focus on innovative and diversified teaching strategies to encourage faculty members to update regularly and adopt innovative pedagogical approaches. Students may be able to engage more enthusiastically and learn diverse teaching styles when faculty members use updated methods in the classroom.
3. Students are not applying theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios. The heads and teachers need to increase the opportunities for experiential learning through internships, real-world projects, and collaborative research in which students can connect theory with practice. Such experiences may be of great importance to students as they can connect their academic learning with real-world applications, thereby improving their overall educational development.
4. Faculty diversity is positively perceived in relation to classroom discussion and student learning, but it lacks a presence in faculty as effective mentors or role models. The university administration may create programs for connecting students to diverse faculty in mentoring, research, or academic advisement, which might more effectively realize the potential benefits of faculty diversity in achieving the success of its students outside of the classroom.

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